

Social media & web report

This social media and web report summarizes visually data extracted from the IPERION HS website and social media over the last year (**October 2021 - September 2022**).

The report highlights strengths and weaknesses in the IPERION HS communication strategy and offers useful insight to identify the audience, monitor engagement and schedule targeted contents.

Google Analytics

report

Italy
United States
United Kingdom
Spain
France
Netherlands
Germany
Greece
China
Portugal

Countries

Demographics

Unique
visitors

21k

Sessions

35.4k

Page views

91.8k

Average session
duration

00:02:27

Visitors: New vs Returning

20%

Returning visitors

469

users registered

+16,84%

over the last year

USER EXPERIENCE: customization

- users
- sessions
- page views

Average duration session

00:02:27

Page		Page Views	% Page Views
1. /	10.94%		
2. /my-account/	5.24%		
3. /iperion-hsaccess/	3.21%		
4. /fixlab/	2.76%		
5. /the-insitumlab-analytical-infrastructure-for-non-destructive-in-situ-studies-of-cultural-heritage-in-munich-opens-two-phd-positions-deadline-on-october-30-2022/	2.69%		
6. /lectures-series/	2.57%		
7. /cart/	2.52%		
8. /dashboard/	2.46%		
9. /lecture-1-2022/	2.25%		
10. /molab/	1.96%		

Behaviour

Average Rate
58,88%

Bounce Rate

The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. The bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds

Channels

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

97,78%

Social media (mostly Facebook, but also Twitter and LinkedIn) drive users towards the events of IPERION HS (webinars, doctoral summer schools, calls, etc...)

IPERION HS

report

A white network diagram consisting of four circular nodes connected by lines. The nodes are arranged in a zig-zag pattern: the first node is at the bottom left, the second is at the top middle, the third is at the bottom right, and the fourth is at the top right. The word 'report' is written in white lowercase letters above the nodes, with the 'o' in 'report' positioned between the second and third nodes.

Italy
Spain
Greece
Portugal
France
Malta
United Kingdom
Brazil
Egypt
Germany

Countries

Demographics

Followers

1.378

Posts

210

Shares

765

Page
engagement

5.2k

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

16,98%

New followers

Sentiment

IPERION HS engages at any hour

HERITAGE INTERPRETATION AND MONITORING

NICOLA MASINI

Iperion HS
Feb 25, 08:21

Remote sensing offers a unique approach to investigate and monitor #culturalheritage & landscapes. In the next #HSAcademy webinar, Nicola Masini will present technologies and case studies. March 8th, 2022 at 3 pm CET Register: <https://bit.ly/3JPT42M> #heritagescience ISPC CNR Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale E-

8,633 impressions
4.35 % engagement rate

Remote sensing offers a unique approach to investigate and monitor #culturalheritage & landscapes. In the nex...
Published by Laura Benassi · 25 February ·

Some insights are only available when the total is at least 100.

Post impressions 8,955 Post reach 8,029 Post engagement 503

Interactions

200 12 0 1 0 0

Reactions 213

Comments 20

Link clicks 60

Shares 24

Other clicks 169

Iperion HS
Feb 11, 09:06

Iperion HS and E-rihs.eu celebrate the international day of #WomenInScience and thank all the women heritage scientists for the great work they do every day! #February11 #heritagescience European Commission UNESCO Heritage Research Hub ICCROM - conserving culture, promoting diversity

46 shares
12 % engagement rate

Top impressions

Top shares

Iperion HS
21 March ·

Heritage Scientists at the Budapest Neutron Centre are working on interesting multidisciplinary projects: from an #Atzec mask to ancient potteries. If you are curious to learn more about non-invasive approaches to heritage, visit the Iperion HS or Budapest Neutron Centre websites: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/> <https://www.bnc.hu/> #heritagescience #neutron

Energiatudományi Kutatóközpont
18 March ·

Heritage Sciences at the Budapest Neutron Centre. Interesting projects from an Aztec mask to a 6th century pottery.

EK-CER.HU
Heritage Sciences at the Budapest Neutron Centre - Energiatudományi Kutatóközpont

10

Heritage Scientists at the Budapest Neutron
Centre...

Iperion HS
Mar 21, 08:19

Heritage Scientists at the Budapest Neutron Centre are working on interesting multidisciplinary projects: from an #Atzec mask to ancient potteries. If you are curious to learn more about non-invasive approaches to heritage, visit the Iperion HS or Budapest Neutron Centre websites: <http://www.iperionhs.eu/> <https://ww>

47.22 % engagement rate

Top engagement rate

Top post

55,51%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

IPERION HS

report

Followers

1049

Posts

246

Shares

893

Page
engagement

2.7k

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

26,5%

New followers

Sentiment

IPERION HS @iperion_hs · Mar 9

1st Iperion HS #Training Camp: the programme is OUT now! A unique hands-on experience for #heritagescience focusing on #paleontology and #paleoanthropology, organized by @CENIEH. Apply by 30th of April 2022. Check it here: bit.ly/3tFrdMd...

35 26 0

Impressions ⓘ Engagements ⓘ Detail expands ⓘ

6,282 **225** **40**

New followers ⓘ Profile visits ⓘ

0 **27**

Top engagement

IPERION HS @iperion_hs · Nov 11, 2021

Prestigious permanent #JobOpportunity as a Senior lecturer in conservation science/heritage science at @goteborgsuni bit.ly/3F5Duxx @ErihsEu @HeritageR_Hub @IIC_

16 20 0

Impressions ⓘ Engagements ⓘ Detail expands ⓘ

11,952 **144** **20**

New followers ⓘ Profile visits ⓘ

0 **18**

Top impressions

IPERION HS @iperion_hs · Mar 24

In art, pigments and morphology of surfaces can be investigated with hyper and #multispectral imaging. How to apply them to support and monitor restoration and intervention for conservation? Join the next #HSAcademy webinar on April 5....

36 27 0

Impressions ⓘ Engagements ⓘ Detail expands ⓘ

3,378 **140** **38**

New followers ⓘ Profile visits ⓘ

0 **8**

Top retweets

Top tweets

Engagement
Impressions

35,76%
VIRAL

99,71%

Amplification Rate percentage

It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

IPERION HS

report

A dark grey network diagram consisting of four circular nodes connected by lines. The nodes are arranged in a zig-zag pattern: the first node is at the bottom left, the second is at the top middle, the third is at the bottom right, and the fourth is at the top right. The word 'report' is positioned above the nodes, with the 'o' in 'report' aligned with the second node.

Follower demographics

Location ▾

London Area, United Kingdom, United Kingdom · 65 (4.7%)

The Randstad, Netherlands, Netherlands · 50 (3.6%)

Greater Rome Metropolitan Area, Italy · 41 (2.9%)

Florence, Italy Metropolitan Area, Italy · 40 (2.9%)

Greater Paris Metropolitan Region, France · 38 (2.7%)

Greater Madrid Metropolitan Area, Spain · 34 (2.4%)

Greater Milan Metropolitan Area, Italy · 30 (2.1%)

Greater Turin Metropolitan Area, Italy · 20 (1.4%)

Athens Metropolitan Area, Greece · 19 (1.4%)

Antwerp Metropolitan Area, Belgium · 18 (1.3%)

countries

Followers

1381

Posts

150

Page shares

378

Page views

44K

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

50,90%

+703

New followers

Heritage Science Online Forum
1,397 followers
10mo · 🌐

#archlab
#heritagescience for special books...

CRC Centre de Recherche sur la Conservation · 1st
11mo · 🌐

Analyses par fluorescence des rayons X sur un corpus de bibles historiques enluminées du XIVème siècle conservées à la BNF.
Lucie Cooper, Eléonora Pellizzi, Sabine MAFFRE, Marie Radepo: ...see more

See translation

Heritage Science Online Forum
Jan 09, 08:45

#archlab #heritagescience for special books...

20.25 % engagement rate

with Oulfa Belhadj and 2 others

Top engagement

Heritage Science Online Forum
Aug 03, 09:01

Iperion HS User experience 4: The conservation research group of Universitat de Barcelona recently carried out, thanks to MOLAB, the study of some bromoils (a peculiar photographic technique dating back to the first half of the 20th century) belonging

1,927 impressions
4.83 % engagement rate

Top impressions

Webinar #06 / October, 12th 2021

ARTS AND HUMANITIES
& IPERION HS
STEFAN BELISHKI, JOAN ABELA & JOANN CASSAR
DISCUSS WITH HERITAGE SCIENTISTS

Heritage Science Online Forum
Oct 05, 09:22

The next #HSAcademy webinar will be held on October 12 at 3 pm CEST: Stefan Belishki from E.C.C.O. European Confederation of Conservator-Restorers Organizations and Joan Abela from the University of Malta together with JoAnn CASSAR discuss with heritage

22 shares
14.6 % engagement rate

Top shares

Top posts

378

Shares

85K

Impressions

0,44%
VIRAL

27,37%

Amplification Rate percentage

Comparing some data

Google

Italy - United States - United Kingdom - Spain - France - Netherlands - Germany - Greece - China - Portugal

Facebook

Italy - Spain - Greece - Portugal - France - Malta - United Kingdom - Brazil - Egypt - Germany

LinkedIn

United Kingdom - the Netherlands - Italy - France - Spain - United States - Greece

Location

Google

Male 54.15% Female 45.85%
Age 25-34

Facebook

Male 23.5% Female 76.5%
Age 25-44

User's identikit

Google

469

Facebook

1.378

Twitter

1049

Linkedin

1381

Users: numbers

+**1336** new followers
on social media
and +**79** new users registered
in the website
in the last year

#HeritageScience

NUMBER OF MENTIONS

heritagescience

145

%

TOTAL IMPRESSIONS

heritagescience

35k

%

ALL SOURCES

● Twitter
● Websites

● Instagram

<https://app.mediatoolkit.com>

<https://app.mediatoolkit.com> © Natural Earth

Top countries

Top languages

Spelling variants used

SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

Positive Neutral Negative <https://app.mediatoolkit.com>

SENTIMENT BY SOURCES

Positive Neutral Negative

<https://app.mediatoolkit.com>

Search Twitter Hashtags

Twitter Suggestions

Instagram

heritagescience

Track

#history

#STEM

#conservation

#imaging

#CulturalHeritage

#olfactory

#scud2016

#IconTF16

#seahaconf2016

#seahaconf

To get suggestions for your posts, [start the free trial](#) and track your Twitter account

26

POPULARITY

0

RECENT POPULARITY

0%

MONTH TREND

0%

WEEK TREND

Get Full Analysis

Related Hashtags

CORRELATION POPULARITY

#heritagescience
#imaging #seahaconf2016
#conservation
#scud2016 #history #seahaconf
#IconTF16 #STEM #olfactory
#CulturalHeritage

Mostly Tweeted By

ALL-TIME RECENT

Influence

Specialization

Followers

Show more

See Top Tweets

popularity trends

Google

97,78%

Facebook

16,98%

Twitter

26,50%

Linkedin

50,90%

Audience Grow Rate Percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

It is the rate at which
your followers take
your content and
share it through their
networks
(Avinash Kaushik, Google)

Facebook
55,5%

Twitter
99,7%

Linkedin
27,4%

Amplification Rate Percentage

IPERION HS Social Media & Web Report
(October 2021-September 2022)

Author: Laura Benassi

Year: November 2022

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